

**FACE-TO-FACE INSTRUCTION vis-à-vis PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND
TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL:
MANAGEMENT PLAN**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 8

Pages: 1162-1180

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2807

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14567692

Manuscript Accepted: 12-17-2024

Face-To-Face Instruction vis-à-vis Parental Involvement and Teachers' Performance in Public Elementary School: Management Plan

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Abstract

The implementation of face-to-face instruction brought unique challenges and breakthroughs in the educational landscape. During the implementation, teachers cannot do it alone; they need an extra hand. The parents can assist teachers in providing quality education to the learners. Limited studies focused on how face-to-face interaction with the parent's involvement is facilitated. This study assessed the implementation of face-to-face instruction in connection with the parents' involvement and teachers' performance in Moalboal District as a basis for a management plan. This study utilized the triangulation mixed-method research design wherein there is no sequence in gathering the data. With random and stratified sampling techniques, 278 respondents were chosen to participate in this study. The instruments used in this study were adopted. The data gathered were analyzed and treated according to the statistical analysis and qualitative analysis used in this study. The results showed that there is a significant relationship between the parents' involvement and the teachers' performance, with a p-value of 0.00. As to the parents' and teachers' observations and experiences, there are three emerging themes – Poor, Pause, and Persistence. With this, education was greatly affected by the pandemic, and the kind of traditional classroom setup now called face-to-face instruction is not the same as before. This means emerging and innovative instructional strategies are required to increase the retention, focus, and motivation of the learners. It is recommended in this study that a management plan be crafted to strengthen the collaboration of teachers and parents.

Keywords: *educational Management, face-to-face instruction, parent involvement, triangulation mixed method, Moalboal District*

Introduction

In this post era of the pandemic, teachers and parents need to have a strong collaboration on how to improve the academic performance of the learners. Having hindsight of what had happened during the pandemic, parents played a significant role in assisting students through complying with different academic tasks such as modules and other supplementary activities while teachers are more focused on assessing how far the learners understand the concept even if they were not around through checking the modules (Abucejo et al., 2022). Today, the responsibilities of the parents and teachers continue (Ando et al., 2022). It is pivotal to have a lens of how learners are coping with their academic responsibilities that would affect the teachers' performance (Kustantri et al., 2021). In the literature that talks about parents' involvement in classroom instruction, none focused on how this affects the teachers' performance after the pandemic (Akbar et al., 2017).

This study assessed the face-to-face instruction in connection to the parents' involvement and teachers' performance to see the highlights and limitations of how parents and teachers influence and affect learners' lives. A management plan can be construed as strengthening the pedagogy of how teachers manage the classroom. The effect of the learners' performance can be reflected in the teachers' performance (Aimah & Purwanto, 2019).

Under DepEd order number 13 series of 2022 also known as the Omnibus Guidelines of the Regulation of Operations of Parent-Teacher Associations, teachers, parents, and the community should be working hand-in-hand in promoting a harmonious relationship and productive engagement for the learners' welfare. It is further indicated that partnerships and collaborative initiatives can be instituted to facilitate a classroom that is conducive to learning. This DepEd order is also anchored from the Philippine Constitution wherein the stipulation of providing quality education was written under Article 14 section 1. This implies that parents and teachers are vital instruments in forwarding academic progress among the learners wherein the learners' development is the reference of the teachers' performance. This study intends to create a plan on how the roles that parents and teachers played in the learners' educational journey are positively sustained and constantly assessed to seek better results.

During the pandemic, parents and the other members of the family are ones who were in charge in helping the learners accomplish the modules (Collado et al., 2023). Parents or older siblings are asked to go to the school for the distribution and retrieval of the modules and other supplementary activities (Castroverde & Acala, 2021). The task of getting and submitting the modules is not just the primary responsibility of the parents but on how to answer the modules (Michelson et al., 2021). Parents are of different educational backgrounds and orientations. Some parents assist their children actively while others are passive (Idulog, 2022). Some parents are not even sure if they are teaching the concepts in the modules correctly (Anoda, 2022). Some parents may just let it leave as blank as they don't know the answers. While children are also of the same context wherein, they may or may not answer the modules (Reimers et al., 2020). These situations posed a challenge on how teachers can cope with the lost time of teaching the concepts correctly and on how teachers can turn the table positively so learners' needs will be catered.

Teachers are the recipients of the backdoor effect of the pandemic (Del Mundo-Sales et al., 2022). The backdoor effect in this context is the domino effect brought by the pandemic that constantly affects the learners' academic experience. The transitions during and after the pandemic created a massive impact on how students behave, learn, comprehend, analyze, and even communicate (Leoveras et al., 2023). The basic way of learners' routine is overshadowed by the number of months staying inside their homes with limited spaces and dormant physical and mental exercise. Teachers are tasked to look into the different strategies, methods, and techniques that can harness the learners' way of learning. It is significant to see how the collaboration of the teachers and the parents creates a picture of shared responsibility in addressing the most pressing issues of the learners' academic development. This study draws its line on evaluating the face-to-face instruction utilized by the Department of Education in connection to the parents' involvement and teachers' performance in creating a management plan for the teachers.

Research Questions

This research assessed the face-to-face instruction in connection with the parental involvement and teachers' performance of Moalboal District, Moalboal, Cebu for the school year 2023-2024 as a basis for an enhancement plan. Specifically, this answered the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents:
 - 1.1. Teacher; and
 - 1.1.1. age;
 - 1.1.2. gender;
 - 1.1.3. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.1.4. length of teaching experience; and
 - 1.1.5. marital status?
 - 1.2. Parent?
 - 1.2.1. age;
 - 1.2.2. gender;
 - 1.2.3. socio-economic status; and
 - 1.2.4. marital status?
2. What is the level of Face-to-Face Instruction implementation as perceived and observed by the teachers as to:
 - 2.1. learners' behavior;
 - 2.2. knowledge of the subject matter; and
 - 2.3. learners' comprehension and analysis?
3. What is the level of parents' involvement as perceived by the parents and validated by the teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. parenting;
 - 3.2. communication;
 - 3.3. volunteering;
 - 3.4. learning at home; and
 - 3.5. decision making and collaborating with the community?
4. What is the teachers' performance in terms of their Classroom Observation results under the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF)?
5. Are there significant relationships among the following:
 - 5.1. demographic profile;
 - 5.2. level of perception of face-to-face Instruction as perceived by the teachers and parents;
 - 5.3. parents' involvement; and
 - 5.4. the teachers' performance?
6. What are the observations and learning experiences of the teachers and the parents in face-to-face instruction?
7. What recommendations can be crafted based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a triangulation mixed-method research design. This design has no specific sequence for gathering the quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative data used descriptive-correlational research design to correlate the data coming from the respondents' perception towards the Face-to-Face instruction to the parents' involvement and their performance. The qualitative data used descriptive qualitative research design with the thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke to surface and describe the different learning experiences of the parents and the teachers.

Respondents

This study utilized random and stratified sampling techniques wherein every school in the Moalboal district will be represented. With the 15 identified schools in Moalboal, this study randomly picks numbers that would depend on the number of teachers in a specific school and seven (7) parent-respondents. The teachers are currently teaching from any level. The parent-respondents may have one or

more children studying in the different schools in Moalboal District. The process of practicing randomization is through the drawlots procedure, and whoever picks the one with the signature will be part of the study. This applies to both teachers and parents as respondents of the study. A total of 278 teachers and parents were respondents to the study.

Instrument

This study utilized one instrument for the two sets of respondents for gathering the quantitative data and another semi-structured interview guide for eliciting qualitative data. For the quantitative, the researcher will be using an adapted questionnaire containing the demographic profile of the respondents and the questions about Face-to-Face instruction in connection with the parent's involvement and teacher's performance. Aboagye (2021) will be used for the Face-to-Face instruction instrument. Akimoff (1996) will be used for the Parent Involvement instrument. Further, the study will also utilize an interview guide question to triangulate the quantitative data. The questions center on the observations, challenges, and suggestions of the parents and teachers. These questions are translated into vernacular for better understanding. The quantitative instrument was an adopted questionnaire. According to Colton & Covert (2007), the adopted instrument will go through face validity, which is to check the superficial of the items to be conducted by the researcher, and Content Validity, which the researcher will ask experts in the field to validate every item for appropriateness. The qualitative interview guide questions were also screened and reviewed by experts. The original five questions were compressed into three which is to elicit the parent's and teachers' observations, challenges, and suggestions. With this, the instruments used in this study are valid and reliable.

Results and Discussion

The following tables answered the statement of the problem that this study formulated.

Table 1. *Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
30 years and below	37	21.4%
31-40	101	58.4%
41-50	20	11.6%
51-above	15	8.6%
Total	173	100%

Table 1 presents the age of the respondents. There are 173 respondents, and the majority of them are in the age group 31-40 with 101 counts (58.4%), while the lowest count among the age groups belongs to 51 and above with 15 respondents (8.6%). With these counts, it can be understood that most of the respondents are not new teachers.

These teachers rendered 5 years or more in the teaching profession. It can be seen as well that there are veteran teachers who served the department for more than 20 to 30 years. With this, the gathering of the data will be well-represented among the age groups (Rahayu & Wirza, 2020).

The age of the teachers can be a potent instrument in understanding the learners. The style of teaching and even the utilization of the teaching strategies may be influenced by age (Guillen-Gamez & Mayorga-Fernandez, 2020). Teachers who are new in the field can impart fresh ideas and technologically driven methods and approaches while experienced teachers can provide wisdom and real-based encounters on how to manage the class (Gharti-Chhetri, 2022). However, according to Abdulahi (2020), age is not a prime determiner of how good a teacher is or how effective he or she can deliver the classroom instruction, it is through how the teacher teaches the best way possible to let the learners attain meaningful learning experiences.

Table 2. *Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	16	9.2%
Female	157	90.8%
Total	173	100%

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage of the respondent's gender. Of the 173 respondents, 16 of them are male or 9.2% while the rest are female with 157 counts (90.8%). This implies that in the total sample of this study, the female respondents dominated. This is not a question when the social norms are being served as the reference (Hoorens et al., 2021; Okoye et al., 2020). Even before, teaching was a profession that most women would like to land (Llorens et al., 2021; Starr & Simpkins, 2021).

However, Copur-Gencturk et al. (2021) said that it is not always a guarantee that female teachers are more effective than male teachers because there are some instances that which male teachers are better than female in the teaching profession.

In the implementation of face-to-face instruction, the teachers' gender was tested. While more female teachers are more patient than male teachers, some male teachers can establish discipline right away compared to female teachers (Binderkrantz & Bisgaard, 2024). In terms of how the professional relationship between the teacher and the parents is concerned, more female teachers can connect to mothers and guardians. However, this is not true all the time. There are teachers whether male or female can easily establish good communication among the parents of the learners (Kreitzer & Sweet-Cushman, 2021).

Table 3. *Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bachelors	44	25.4%
With Units in Masters	111	64.2%
Masters	18	10.4%
Total	173	100%

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage of the respondents' highest educational attainment. Of the total number of respondents, 111 of them, or 64.2% have units in masters while only 18 of them are masters degree holders already. Although the rest of the respondents are bachelor's degree holders, the number can speak so much of how eager the teachers are to continue their academic ladder. This is a good indication that the majority of the teachers are currently studying for their master's degree. This implies that most of the teachers in the Department of Education are highly equipped with current strategies that can improve the academic performance of the learners (Comighud & Arevalo, 2021; Lee & Lee, 2020).

The hiring procedure in the Department of Education requires teachers not just passers of the licensure examination but also to start with their masters. This creates a domino effect of increasing productivity inside the classroom wherein teachers' experiences in post-graduate education can be tried and tested (Jimenez, 2020). Since learners are changing and becoming more adept in technology, it is deemed proper that teachers should be well-versed in terms of utilizing technological tools inside the classroom (Van den Broeck et al., 2020). With this, the teachers are not left behind in terms of how advanced the learners are. This is the main reason why teachers should continue acquiring helpful knowledge not just in post-graduate education but also in relevant seminars, workshops, and training (Oliveira et al., 2021).

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage of the respondents' length of service. Of the total number of respondents, 106 of them, or 61.3% rendered 5-9 years in the teaching profession while 7 of them, or 4.1% have been in the profession for 15-19 years. This means that the teachers acquired reasonable number of years to share their professional observations regarding face-to-face instruction especially right after the pandemic. With this, it is expedient to correlate the length of service among teachers to the different variables established in this study (Marshall et al., 2020).

Table 4. *Length of Service*

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
0-4	14	8.1%
5-9	106	61.3%
10-14	31	17.9%
15-19	7	4.1%
20-24	0	0%
25 and above	15	8.6%
Total	173	100%

The length of service provides significant success in the organization or school wherein teachers share their expertise transpired from their experiences (Comighud & Arevalo, 2021). The higher the number of years in the field of education the more that the teachers employ positive and desirable attributes inside the classroom (Phytanza & Burhaein, 2020). The length of service reflects stability and reliability because the longer the tenure of the teachers the more they become familiar with the culture, values, and processes in teaching (Papadakis et al., 2021). Moreover, according to Jacobson et al. (2020) when teachers stay longer, it speaks more about mentorship and quality coaching. The new teachers can be given wisdom on how to handle difficult classes. Veteran teachers can lead the new ones to become effective in the teaching-learning process (Walters et al., 2020). With this, veteran teachers make a new wave of teachers who can mold learners to reach their fullest potential.

Table 5. *Marital Status*

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Single	25	14.5%
Married	144	83.2%
Widowed	4	2.3%
Total	173	100%

Table 5 shows the marital status of the respondents. With the total number of respondents, there are 144 or 83.2% married teachers and 4 or 2.3% widowed while there are 25 or 14.5% single teachers. This data can provide an implication that most of the teachers in the field are married. This means that they have responsibilities at home and work. This can interplay with how they sustain their effectiveness in teaching. While married teachers are expected to have so many responsibilities, not all single teachers are burdened with responsibilities, some of them are breadwinners whose first families rely on them (Patriarca, 2023; Puyod, 2023).

Marital status can be a significant factor affecting how a teacher communicates and interacts with fellow teachers, students, parents, and other internal and external stakeholders (Iqbal et al., 2020; Agyapong et al., 2022). There are times when married teachers become biased in making decisions or in setting their perspective because they have experience as parents (Sharma & Rajput, 2021). However,

teachers are provided with ethical standards in sustaining impartiality in attending to the needs of the learners. The marital status of the teachers helps understand how they manage face-to-face instruction together with the involvement of their students' parents.

Table 6. *Parent's Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
30 years and below	19	18.10
31-40	45	42.86
41-50	32	30.48
51-above	9	8.57
Total	105	100

Most of the parents are in middle age, as depicted in Table 6. The range 31-40 marked the highest count, while 51 and above garnered the lowest frequency of 9. This data implies that most of the parents have great experience in handling the ups and downs of family life. Most of the parents of this age are emotionally mature and can execute parenting to their children in thoughtful yet consistent parenting. These parents can handle stress better and they can set the priorities and direction of their family in a clearer perspective.

Table 7. *Parent's Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	9	8.57
Female	96	91.43
Total	105	100

Of the 105 parent-respondents, 96 of them are female while 9 of them are male. This data reflects what we can usually see in the school's waiting area. Most of the mothers are staying and waiting for their children to go home. This data does not only represent the biological mothers and fathers but also those guardians and siblings or relatives in the family who are attending to the needs of the children. It can be seen as a fact that mothers and fathers do or execute disciplinary actions differently. They are known to balance the two-sided faces of discipline such as fathers being stricter and more impatient while the mothers are more lenient and nurturing.

Most of the parent-respondents answered low-income class with 101 counts. This is followed by the middle-income class of 4 counts. While no one declared to be part of the high-income class. This data projects the reality that since the research environment in the Moalboal District comprises 15 public schools, normally, it would be in this range – low-income class.

Table 8. *Parent's Socio-Economic Status*

<i>Socio-Economic Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Low-Income Class	101	96.19%
Middle-Income Class	4	64.2%
High-Income Class	0	0
Total	105	100%

The socio-economic status of the parents shows the reason why they enrolled their children in public schools. With this, most of the children are having problems in school in terms of their attitude and behavior brought by the problems they experienced at home, such as arguing regarding monetary issues. Socioeconomic status greatly affects how parents take care of their children, especially in providing for the children's needs.

Table 9. *Parent's Marital Status*

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Single	26	23.42%
Married	83	74.77
Widowed	2	1.80%
Total	105	100%

Most of the parents are married, with 83 counts, while there are 26 single parents and two (2) widowed. This data implies that most of the children have married parents. Having married parents means stability, as mothers and fathers share their responsibilities in providing the best shelter for their children. Parents can divide their workload into nurturing their children compared to those who are single parents who take the majority of the parenting responsibilities. Single parents tend to experience burnout and high levels of stress as they try to balance their work and life after work.

The Level Of Face-To-Face Instruction Implementation As Perceived By The Teachers

Face-to-face instruction was implemented right after the government secured and announced that it was safe for the learners to go to school. With this, all schools are required to have health protocols that will not compromise the health of the learners (De Dominico et al., 2021). Aside from the health protocols, teachers employ different strategies in teaching the lesson. Coupled with the observation of the teachers, learners are having a hard time learning the most essential competencies (Reimers et al., 2020). This was exacerbated by the learner's behavior. The behavior was attributed to the home quarantines that they experienced (Liu et al., 2021).

Table 10 presents face-to-face instruction implementation as perceived by the teachers. The data shows that the face-to-face instruction

implementation as perceived by the teachers agreed with all the statements with an average weighted mean of 3.87. This means that in terms of its implementation, the teachers can perceive that the learners are having challenges and difficulties in their behavior inside the classroom as this was disturbed during the pandemic, their knowledge of the subject matter wherein their parents usually answer their modules and other supplementary materials, and the learners' comprehension and analysis that even simple sentences are difficult for them to understand (Haddad et al., 2020; Panda et al., 2021; Francisco et al., 2020).

Table 10. *The Level of Face-to-Face Instruction Implementation as Perceived by the Teachers*

<i>Face-to-Face Instruction Implementation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Learners' Behavior	3.66	0.61	Agree
1. The learners are too rowdy.	4.04	0.67	Agree
2. The learners cannot follow the classroom routines.	3.48	0.81	Agree
3. The learners tend to loss focus during classroom discussion.	3.98	0.71	Agree
4. The learners are disrespectful.	3.46	0.89	Agree
5. The learners are losing the enthusiasm to finish an academic task.	3.36	0.88	Undecided
Knowledge towards the Subject Matter	3.91	0.63	Agree
1. The learners are having problems on retention.	4.02	0.80	Agree
2. The learners are not well versed in terms of the content they need to master.	3.88	0.69	Agree
3. Some learners lack knowledge on the topic taken in their previous grade level.	3.88	0.80	Agree
4. Learners are having difficulty absorbing the content shared during discussion.	4.02	0.74	Agree
5. Learners are passive in terms of learning the content of the subject matter.	3.74	0.83	Agree
Learners' Comprehension and Analysis	4.05	0.58	Agree
1. Learners cannot easily understand the meaning of a specific phrase or sentence.	3.90	0.65	Agree
2. Learners tend to have a low analysis of situational problems.	4.06	0.74	Agree
3. Learners are having difficulty in inferring.	4.18	0.66	Agree
4. Learners are struggling in summarizing.	4.20	0.64	Strongly Agree
5. Learners cannot merge new information with prior knowledge to form a new idea, perspective, or opinion.	3.90	0.68	Agree
AWM	3.87	0.61	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.79-Strongly Disagree; 1.80-2.59-Disagree; 2.60-3.39-Uncecided; 3.40-4.19-Agree; 4.20-5.00- Strongly Agree

With the indicators under the face-to-face, learners' comprehension and analysis gained the highest mean of 4.05 while learners' behavior garnered the lowest mean of 3.66. This implies that learners' comprehension and analysis are the skills that teachers should be cognizant of in helping them master the most essential learning competencies. It can be noted that among the statements in the face-to-face instruction, the statement, "The learners cannot follow the classroom routines." garnered 3.48 which is the lowest among all statements. This means that of all the behaviors, factors, and indicators that may affect the learners' performance, it is the daily routine that is greatly affected.

According to Garcia and Weiss (2020), the need to reinforce the learners' academic performance and achievement underscores the fact that the routine and pattern of learning among the students were disturbed. This paves the way for how teachers would find appropriate strategies that can augment the challenges inside the classroom (Jena, 2020). Students are expected to master the most essential learning competencies adjusted by the Department of Education to cater to the learners' needs however, the students are still having difficulties even understanding basic questions (Rapanta et al., 2021). With this, it is important to assess the learners' performance, their behavior, and their basic skills in comprehending text and analyzing it in face-to-face instruction.

Parents' Involvement

Parents' involvement is essential in the educative process of the learners (Lawrence & Fakuade, 2021). This can be manifested in how they support their children's talent and potential and how they guide them in the right direction of fulfilling their dreams and aspirations in life (Ribeiro et al., 2021). The active involvement of the parents can be traced to how they support their children in different academic and non-academic activities (Kartel et al., 2022). It takes a village to raise a child and with this, parents and teachers should work hand in hand in molding the behavior, character, attitude, and potential of every child (Tan et al., 2020).

Table 11 shows the level of parents' involvement. The indicators under parent's involvement include parenting (mean = 3.74), communication (mean = 3.40), volunteering (mean = 3.38), learning at home (mean = 3.46), and decision-making and collaborating with the community (mean = 3.76). As validated by the teachers, the indicators such as parenting (mean = 3.48), communication (mean = 3.29), volunteering (mean = 3.17), learning at home (mean = 3.22), and decision-making and collaborating with the community (mean = 3.59) garnered lower scores but with the same verbal interpretation as the rating of the parents. It can be gleaned that the average mean is 3.53, and it is interpreted as agree. This means that all the statements and indicators are being agreed upon and observed by the teachers regarding how the parents are extending their support and involvement with their children's school activities.

Parents' involvement can be manifested in how parents monitor the academics of their children (Yulianti et al., 2021). It is important that they also have a certain limitation on how they intervene with the homework and assignments of their children (Berkowitz et al., 2021). Limited participation among parents is advised when students are given take-home activities (Dingili & Yungungu, 223). Parents as external stakeholders of the school play a significant role in carrying out the school's decision-making, the school vision, mission,

and goals, and progress and improvement of school projects to better the learning atmosphere of the students (Naish et al., 2023). The strong involvement of the parents can be manifested in their attendance in parent-teacher association meetings, school activities, and participation in different academic and non-academic competitions.

Table 11. *The Level of Parents' Involvement*

<i>Parents' Involvement</i>	<i>Parents</i>	<i>Teachers</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Parenting			
1. Parents accepted, agreed, and tolerated the extent of their child's educative process.	3.86	3.50	Agree
2. Parents are very supportive in different learning activities.	4.10	3.60	Agree
3. Parents are concerned when homework instructions are confusing.	3.68	3.49	Agree
4. Parents attend parent-teacher meetings and discussions all the time.	3.48	3.42	Agree
5. Parents monitor the progress of their child academics	3.58	3.40	Agree
Mean	3.74	3.48	Agree
Communication			
1. Parents write a letter if there are some questions and concerns regarding their child's academic performance.	3.12	2.80	Undecided
2. Parents discuss concerns to clear doubts.	3.48	3.41	Agree
3. Parents provide and set proper expectations during the start of the class.	3.42	3.40	Agree
4. Parents follows the right protocol in complaining something.	3.44	3.42	Agree
5. Parents talk to their children for validation and confirm it from their classmates and teacher.	3.54	3.43	Agree
Mean	3.40	3.29	Agree
Volunteering			
1. Parents donate projects in school.	3.70	3.44	Agree
2. Parents offer their expertise to be a speaker in a specific field to help teachers and learners.	2.86	2.65	Undecided
3. Parents serve as working committees to some of the school activities.	3.54	3.41	Agree
4. Parents are active in crafting school policies.	3.14	2.88	Undecided
5. Parents render service whenever they are needed.	3.64	3.48	Agree
Mean	3.38	3.17	Agree
Learning at Home			
1. Learners are offering their ideas learned at home.	3.58	3.45	Agree
2. Parents are helping their children to cope with the lessons.	3.34	2.75	Undecided
3. Parents are assisting their children in complying with school projects.	3.60	3.55	Agree
4. Learners are complying with their assignment.	3.58	3.46	Agree
5. Parents are doing remediation at home.	3.22	2.90	Undecided
Mean	3.46	3.22	Agree
Decision Making and Collaborating with Community			
1. Parents play an integral role in making school decisions.	3.70	3.55	Agree
2. Parents contribute ideas on how projects have materialized and accomplished.	3.70	3.49	Agree
3. Parents are actively participating community activities.	3.74	3.51	Agree
4. Parents are part of the parent-teacher association.	4.14	3.89	Agree
5. Parents are creating ways to help improve the school through the Local Government Unit (LGU)	3.52	3.49	Agree
Mean	3.76	3.59	Agree
AWM	3.53	0.66	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.79-Strongly Disagree; 1.80-2.59-Disagree; 2.60-3.39-Undecided; 3.40-4.19-Agree; 4.20-5.00- Strongly Agree

The Teachers' Performance In Terms Of The Latest Ipcrf Rating

In gauging the performance of the teachers, the Department of Education (DepEd) initiated the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) as provided by the law indicated in the Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 06, series of 2012 which sets the guidelines on the establishment of the implementation of the strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) across all the agencies in the government wherein they need to present the documents and pieces of evidence to show how teachers are performing for the entire school year. These documents are subject to scrutiny and validation among the designated authorities. Assessing the teacher's performance is vital for the teachers to grow personally and professionally (Sancar et al., 2021). Their growth in their profession and their effectiveness in teaching can have a domino effect on the student's academic performance (Tantawy, 2020).

Table 12 presents the teachers' performance in terms of the latest Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) rating for the school year 2022-2023. In the given range of the teacher's rating scale, they will be rated if their score reaches 5.00 which means outstanding and this is the highest, very satisfactory is at 4, satisfactory is at 3, unsatisfactory is at 2, and poor is at 1. It can be gleaned from the table that teachers' ratings interplay between outstanding and very satisfactory. 19 (11%) teachers landed on outstanding while the rest of the 154 (89.0%) garnered very satisfactory. This can be implied that teachers have high ratings which can be traced from their documents and pieces of evidence to justify their claim for their rating.

Table 12. *The Teachers' Performance in Terms of the Latest IPCRF Rating*

<i>IPCRF Rating</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	19	11.0%
Very Satisfactory	154	89.0%
Total	173	100%

The importance of IPCRF underscores the fact that it improves the culture of excellent work ethics that leads to an effective teacher delivering quality institutions inside the classroom. In IPCRF, the specific goals, the key results area, and targets are well defined (Cadag, 2024). This is where teachers are guided on what to achieve at the end of the school year. Further, IPCRF promotes quality coaching and mentoring (Ortiz & Arnado, 2022). The feedback process during IPCRF validation is essential for the teachers to be calibrated with what to present as a purposeful evidence-based claim. This also enhances how the teachers' accountability is transpired in the school workplace. With this, IPCRF helps the teachers to attain continuous improvement within the school organization.

Significant Relationship between the Demographic Profile and The Level of Face-to-Face Instruction Implementation

In the implementation of face-to-face instruction, it is important to look into how the teachers' demographic profiles serve as factors that can affect its implementation. The young teacher's adeptness in the utilization of technology may play a significant factor in how teachers manage the classroom after the pandemic. Teachers who have been in the field of education for quite some time already have a repertoire of teaching strategies in face-to-face instruction (Akojie et al., 2022). The challenge of handling a face-to-face class will be augmented when a teacher has experience with a traditional set-up.

Table 13. *Significant Relationship between the Demographic Profile and The Level of Face-to-Face Instruction Implementation*

	<i>Demographic profile</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
<i>The Level of Face-to-Face Instruction</i>	Age	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Gender	0.66	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Highest Educational Attainment	0.79	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Length of Service	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Marital Status	0.78	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 13 shows the significant relationship between the demographic profile and the level of face-to-face instruction implementation. It can be gleaned that age (p -value = 0.00) and length of service (p -value 0.00) have a significant relationship with the level of face-to-face instruction implementation. This means that after the pandemic, the teachers' age and length of service play an integral role in managing the classroom (Guoyan et al., 2023).

Veteran teachers have experiences with various teaching strategies, methods, and techniques that are tested to be effective in a traditional classroom setup (Li & Yu, 2022). Gender (p -value = 0.66), highest educational attainment (p -value = 0.79), and marital status (p -value = 0.78) have no significant relationship. With this, it can be implied that in the implementation of face-to-face instruction, having a master's or doctoral degree, either a male or female, and being married or single will not have a bearing in managing traditional classroom setup.

Understanding the significant relationship between the demographic profile and the level of face-to-face instruction implementation is tantamount to providing helpful ways on how the designated authorities can tailor the needs of the teachers to maintain the delivery of quality instruction (Sari & Keser, 2021). Not all indicators in the demographic profile of the teachers can influence face-to-face implementation because traditional classroom setup demands a repertoire of tested and effective teaching strategies.

Significant Relationship between the Demographic Profile and The Parents' Involvement

Parents are teachers' partners in raising a child that will soon lead the country. Their involvement is significant in making the learners the best version of themselves (Mann & Gilmore, 2023). The demographic profile of the teachers can influence how the parents are extending their efforts and support towards the school activities (Almendingen et al., 2022). When parents are actively involved in the process of their children's journey in education, it creates a picture of shared responsibility between the teachers and the parents (Hannon & O'Donnell, 2022). With this, the learner will smooth sailing journey of becoming an asset in the community.

Table 14 shows the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the teachers and the parents' involvement. Only age (p -value = 0.01) has a significant association with the parents' involvement. While gender (p -value = 0.69), highest educational attainment (p -value = 0.22), length of service (p -value = 0.68), and marital status (p -value = 0.57) established no significant association with the parents' involvement. This means that the age of the teachers can influence how the parents participate and support the school programs and projects (Azad et al., 2021).

Table 14. *Significant Relationship between the Demographic Profile and The Parents' Involvement*

	<i>Demographic profile</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
<i>Parents' Involvement</i>	Age	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Gender	0.69	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Highest Educational Attainment	0.22	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Length of Service	0.68	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Marital Status	0.57	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null Hypothesis

In fostering the participation and support of the parents in school, it is vital to create a strong and professional relationship with them (Fadhilah & Nurahman, 2021). Parents' involvement is one of the factors that can enhance how learners with difficulties surmount challenges in mastering the essential skills (Nurhayati, 2021). With the help of the parents, teachers' targeted goals are achieved not just with the development of the learners' skills and knowledge but also with the making of instructional materials which are pertinent in creating a classroom environment conducive to acquiring meaningful learning experiences (Al-Hail et al., 2021).

Significant Relationship between the Demographic Profile and The Teachers' Performance

The teachers' performance can be influenced by their demographic profile. If the teacher has already been in the field of education for many years, the learning experiences can be of great help in facing emerging challenges in the face-to-face setup (Sudirman et al., 2021). When the teacher is also married, the responsibility at work and the life after work needs to be balanced (Puyud, 2023; Patriarca, 2023). Teachers need time and resources to achieve the goals and targets stipulated in the IPCRF. Some teachers settle for Very Satisfactory as this does not need so much of pieces of evidence and documentation because they have their family to attend to or they are currently enrolled in their post-graduate education (Parinduri et al., 2023). With this, it is vital to assess how demographic profile affects the teachers' performance.

Table 15 shows the significant relationship between the demographic profile and the teachers' performance. It can be gleaned that age (p-value 0.05), gender (p-value = 0.01), highest educational attainment (p-value = 0.00), length of service (p-value = 0.00), and marital status (p-value = 0.00) have a significant relationship to the teachers' performance. This means that all the indicators under the demographic profile can influence the performance of the teachers (Pamuji & Limei, 2023). This data is important in providing policies and management plans on how teachers can work efficiently and effectively.

Table 15. *Significant Relationship between the Demographic Profile and The Teachers' Performance*

	<i>Demographic profile</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
<i>Teachers' Performance</i>	Age	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Gender	0.01	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Highest Educational Attainment	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Length of Service	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Marital Status	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

The demographic profile of the teachers contributes to the overall educational outcomes of the teachers not just to the teacher's performance (Bardach et al., 2022). Teachers having diverse backgrounds can have a positive impact on the learners making the teaching-learning process unique and engaging (Wang et al., 2022). Acceptance and belongingness prevail when everyone has something unique to offer in classroom discussion (Baumeister & Robson, 2021). Diverse teachers produce a diverse repertoire of teaching methods and strategies. (Espeland & Stige, 2021). When teachers come from different backgrounds, they can connect with learners who are coming from different backgrounds as well (Minkos & Gelbar, 2021). With this, it reduces biases and stereotypes in handling the teaching-learning process (Bardach et al., 2022). Identifying the demographic profile of the teachers can target possible professional undertakings necessary for their growth and development.

Significant Relationship between the Level of Face-to-Face Instruction and the Parents' Involvement and Teachers' Performance

The implementation of face-to-face instruction can be influenced by how parents get involved and engaged in the process of transition from modular instruction to face-to-face interaction (Salamuddin, 2021). It can be noted as well that aside from the parents' involvement, the teachers' performance plays an integral role in implementing face-to-face instruction (Villar et al., 2022). The level of support and involvement of the parents during the modular instruction may be different in today's setup (Gantalao et al., 2023). It is necessary to know how these variables interplay with each other so that, appropriate intervention can be initiated. Ultimately, one of the success indicators of the implementation of face-to-face instruction is anchored on how parents are actively involved and how teachers perform their tasks to teach and mold the minds of the learners (Agaton & Cueto, 2021).

Table 16 presents the significant relationships among the level of face-to-face instruction implementation, parents' involvement, and teachers' performance. It can be gleaned that the parents' involvement (p-value = 0.00) and the teachers' performance (p-value = 0.05) have a significant relationship to the implementation of face-to-face instruction. This implies that the teachers' performance can be influenced by how face-to-face instruction is implemented (El Refae et al., 2021). This is the same with the active involvement of the

parents wherein it affects how the teachers perform their duties and responsibilities inside the classroom (Zagouras et al., 2022). It is pertinent to identify the significant association between these two because it serves as a reference on how the administrators can create action plans to address the most pressing issues on teachers' performance.

Table 16. *Significant Relationships among the Level of Face-to-Face Instruction and the Parents' Involvement and Teachers' Performance*

		<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Teachers' Performance	Parents' Involvement	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	The Level of Face-to-Face Instruction	0.05	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

The purpose of why teachers should perform well is rooted in the reason that when they can effectively teach, it enhances the educational experiences of the learners. Acquiring meaningful learning experiences can be achieved when there is a successful implementation of face-to-face instruction, the active involvement of the parents, and the teachers' effective classroom management (Villar et al., 2022; Gantalao et al., 2022). In face-to-face instruction, teachers and parents are given an equal chance of establishing a strong relationship with their learners or children (Almendingen et al., 2022). With this, it is important to identify how teachers' performance can be affected or influenced by the implementation of face-to-face instruction and the active involvement of the parents so that it can foster a supportive learning environment.

Significant Relationship between the Parents' Involvement and the Teachers' Performance

The involvement of the parents and the teachers' performance is crucial in shaping the learners' potential (Ricker et al., 2021). According to Azad et al. (2021), parents and teachers are in partnership, especially in providing support to content mastery where parents can be the tutor or can hire tutors to make follow-ups of their children's academic progress. If there is a strong connection between the parents and the teachers, it increases the motivation of the learners to do well in class and it fosters a positive learning environment wherein it establishes a strong foundation for lifelong learning (Jung & Sheldon, 2020).

Table 17 shows the significant relationship between the parents' involvement and the teachers' performance. It can be gleaned that there is a significant relationship between the parents' involvement and the teachers' performance with a p-value of 0.00 which rejects the null hypothesis of the study. This implies that teachers' performance can be influenced by the active involvement of the parents. With this, a strong and professional relationship should be maintained by the teachers and parents in carrying out the intended goals and objectives for the learners to have a meaningful educational experience (Villar et al., 2022; Puyod, 2023).

Table 17. *Significant Relationship between the Parents' Involvement and the Teachers' Performance*

		<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Parents' Involvement	Teachers' Performance	0.00	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Parents' involvement in the educational process of their children signifies the intent to collaborate with the teachers to give the best quality education for their children (Chaidi & Drigas, 2020). One of the most important things to remember in establishing a strong connection with the parents is to have good communication with them (Ribeiro et al., 2021). Better communication is vital for the student's academic success (Lawrence & Fakuade, 2021).

Students become motivated and inspired when their parents show a positive relationship with their teachers, especially during parent-teacher conferences where the student's progress is being discussed (Apriyanti, 2020). Parents can align their efforts with the teacher's dedication to bringing out the best in their children (Tan et al., 2020). This creates a supportive framework or network where parents connect with the teachers while teachers communicate with the parents for the success of their children.

The Observations And Learning Experiences Of The Teachers And The Parents In The Face-To-Face Instruction Implementation

It is vital to understand the parents' observations and the teachers' learning experiences regarding the implementation of face-to-face instruction so that an essential management plan can be made to address concerns and challenges during the implementation (Kaguhangire-Barifajio et al., 2023). Creating a management plan for the teachers to teach effectively and to surmount difficulties encountered during the implementation should be given solutions for this can create a ripple effect towards the learners (Emir et al., 2023).

The Observations and Learning Experiences of the Teachers and the Parents in the Face-To-Face Instruction Implementation

Parents provide their comments, suggestions, or observations whenever they notice something that can affect the educational journey of their children, especially when their children transition from modular to face-to-face instruction. Teachers also give their observations and experiences regarding the implementation of face-to-face instruction for enhancement in terms of the learning resources and learning strategies.

When these observations and experiences from the parents and teachers toward the implementation of face-to-face instruction are identified and analyzed, it opens for intellectual discussion on how to address the issues and concerns through a management plan.

Table 18. *The Observations and Learning Experiences of the Teachers and the Parents in the Face-To-Face Instruction Implementation*

Themes	Subthemes	Quotes
Poor	Slow to Slower	The reading comprehension of the students is deteriorating (T1). The students have no retention (T2). Learners lack focus (T3). The students have poor academic performance because they have poor study habits (T6). The students are always looking outside the window because they want to go out and play making them lose their motivation to join classroom activities (T8).
	Tired	Ang akong anak kay pirmi kapoy pag abot sa balay katong nag sugod na ang face-to-face instruction (P1). My child is always tired once he gets home ever since the start of the face-to-face instruction. Dili na masugo akong anak pag abot sa balay (P2). My child cannot be asked to do something once he comes home from school. Kung akong taparan akong anak para magtuon mi kay 5 minutes ra kapoyan na dayon sya (P3). If I will help my child to study his lessons, he gets tired and the longest time he can stay would be 5 minutes.
Pause	Find time to target the Root Cause	Teachers should assess the learners' capacity to understand and learn the subject matter to provide appropriate strategies (T4). Parents can help in identifying what actions can be considered helpful in understanding the behavior and attitude of the learners (T2). Learners are not focused well on classroom discussions, and I think this is because of the impact of modular learning wherein they let their parents finish their academic tasks (T5).
	Knowing the nature of a child	Sa akong na obserbahan, ang mga bata hilig jud sa dula. Katong nagpandemic, wala jud sila kagawas kayo maong pag sugod na sa klase, ang ilang hunahuna kay sige ra ug dula. Maskin sa balay pag abot gikan sa skwelahan kay ibutang ra ang bag dayon mogawas sa balay kay magdula. Unta mas nindot kung bibo sa klase nila nga nagtuon nya ipa ag isa dula para malingaw ang mga bata (P2). From what I have observed, children are very fond of playing. During the pandemic, they were not allowed to go out to play, so when the class starts especially in face-to-face instruction, they always think of playing. When they arrive from school, they just leave their bag and go out to play. I hope that in school, teachers will have a lot of games so that the children will learn while having fun. Ang mga bata kay nadistorbo jud ang ilang paagi sa pagtuon tungod sa pandemic labi na katong nagmodular sila kay dili man gani ko kasabot sa ubang naa sa modules unsa nalang kaha ang mga bata maong ako nalang ang mag answer. Dili man sila bogo pero nadaut lang jud ang paagi nila sa pagtuon kay kana akong anak kung tutoran nako sa unsa kay maka balo man siya pero karun kay maglisud na (P5). The children's way of learning was disturbed due to the pandemic especially the modular instruction. I cannot understand some of the content in the module, how much more the children that's why I am the one answering it. My son is not stupid or dull not to understand the lesson, it is just that they way of learning was ruined during the pandemic because my son was good and can understand right away when I tutored him before but today, he is having difficulty understanding the lesson.
Persistence	Repertoire of teaching strategies	Varied strategies should be employed in managing the classroom (T4) One of the best ways to alleviate the challenges that teachers are experiencing is to increase the level of patience. Patience. Patience. And Patience (T5). Teachers should conduct daily remediation to help those learners who are struggling with numeracy and literacy (T1).
	Constant involvement	Isip usa ka ginikanan, importante kaayo nga apil kami sa pag pa edukar sa among mga anak kay ebutang ta sa ilang kinaiya, mas nakaila mi kay kami ang ginikanan ug gusto nako nga akoy modisiplina sa akong anak kung magbinadlong (P2). As a parent, it is very important that we participate in educating our children because we know their behavior, and we know better because we are their parents and I want to personally discipline my children. Naay mga panahon nga dili ko kaadto sa tulunghaan busa mamalihug rako sa akong silingan kay dili ko gusto nga dili maakahibalo kung unsa nay mga kasikas sa skwelahan kabahin sa performance sa akong anak (P1). There are times when I can't go to school due to some important reasons, so I ask my neighbor in my behalf because I don't want to miss anything and on what is going on in the school especially regarding my child's academic performance. Importante kau nga moamot jud mi kung nay amotay kay kabalo man pod mi nga naajuy makita sa mga proyekto sa mga masetra para rapod man na sa among mga anak (P5). It is important to share whatever is being agreed regarding an amount to make the project possible and I can see the output and where my money goes and anyway, this is for my child.

P = parents; T= teachers

There are three themes generated from the observations and experiences of the parents and teachers in the implementation of face-to-face instruction as depicted in Table 19. It can be gleaned that the three themes which are the Poor, Pause, and Persistent showcase the importance of knowing what to do to better the classroom environment starting from capacitating the teachers. All these themes will be discussed below with the quotes and words from the teachers and parents together with the related literature.

Theme 1: Poor

Learners' reading, writing, and counting skills are getting worse after the pandemic (Liu et al., 2021). It is noticed that they lack focus in classroom discussions. Their retention has deteriorated (Francisco et al., 2020). They have poor academic performance as observed by the teachers and their parents (Reimers et al., 2020). This theme provides a clear picture that the learners are having difficulties in learning especially in mastering the skills and competencies. This can be corroborated by the words of the parents and the teachers,

Teacher 1 said,

The reading comprehension of the students is deteriorating.

This was supported by Teacher 2 who stated,

The students have no retention.

Teacher 3 added,

Learners lack focus.

Teacher 6 narrated that,

The students have poor academic performance because they have poor study habits.

While Teacher 8 explained that,

The students are always looking outside the window because they want to go out and play making them lose their motivation to join classroom activities.

These are the words of the teachers regarding their experiences in the implementation of face-to-face instruction. Learners are indeed in need of help in coping with and mastering the most essential learning competencies parallel to their grade level. Teachers should pay attention to what is revealed from the data that learners are poor in reading comprehension, no retention, lack of focus, and poor in establishing study habits.

Some parents also shared their observations regarding the implementation of face-to-face instruction. Parent 1 said,

Ang akong anak kay pirmi kapoy pag abot sa balay katong nag sugod na ang face-to-face instruction (My child is always tired once he gets home ever since the start of the face-to-face instruction.)

This was seconded by Parent 2 who mentioned that,

Dili na masugo akong anak pag abot sa balay (My child cannot be asked to do something once he comes home from school.)

Parent 3 also shared that,

Kung akong taparan akong anak para magtuon mi kay 5 minutes ra kapoyan na dayon sya

(If I will help my child to study his lessons, he gets tired and the longest time he can stay would be 5 minutes.)

Parents are concerned regarding their children. They noticed that their children were changing. Parents cannot ask their children to do something at home. Parents are asking their children to do house chores to develop life skills. If this is gone, what will happen to their children? Parents observed that the implementation of face-to-face instruction paves the way for how their children are getting poor academic performance (Liu et al., 2021).

Theme 2: Pause

This theme captures the essence of self-evaluation or reflection in understanding the problem and how to find solutions to it. Teachers and parents should collaborate in understanding their children (Ricker et al., 2021; Azad et al., 2021). Finding the root cause of their children's poor academic performance necessitates a careful examination of their actions (Tan et al., 2020). Teachers can look for assessments and strategies to see how will change the current status of the learner's academic performance. This can be substantiated by the experiences of the teachers and the observations of the parents.

Teacher 4 said that,

Teachers should assess the learners' capacity to understand and learn the subject matter to provide appropriate strategies.

This is supported by the Teacher 2, who mentioned that,

Parents can help in identifying what actions can be considered helpful in understanding the behavior and attitude of the learners

Teacher 5 added that,

Learners are not focused well on classroom discussions, and I think this is because of the impact of modular learning wherein they let their parents finish their academic tasks.

Teachers should have various teaching strategies and methods for managing the class. The diversity of the learners should be a good reason for the teachers to innovate and provide unique experiences among the learners. Teachers cannot do it all alone, they need the help of the parents who can make follow-ups regarding the academic performance of the learners.

The observations of the parents help make essential programs that can facilitate the increase of the learners' academic performance and how teachers are being assisted in delivering quality instruction. This can be corroborated by their words on how the parents explain their observations in the implementation of the face-to-face instruction.

Parent 2 narrated that,

Sa akong na obserbahan, ang mga bata hilig jud sa dula. Katong nagpandemic, wala jud sila kagawas kayo maong pag sugod na sa klase, ang ilang hunahuna kay sige ra ug dula. Maskin sa balay pag abot gikan sa skwelahan kay ibutang ra ang bag dayon mogawas sa balay kay magdula. Unta mas nindot kung bibo sa klase nila nga nagtuon nya ipa ag isa dula para malingaw ang mga bata (From what I have observed, children are very fond of playing. During the pandemic, they were not allowed to go out to play, so when the class starts especially in face-to-face instruction, they always think of playing. When they arrive from school, they just leave their bag and go out to play. I hope that in school, teachers will have a lot of games so that the children will learn while having fun.)

Another parent also shared and Parent 5 explained that,

Ang mga bata kay nadisturbo jud ang ilang paagi sa pagtuon tungod sa pandemic labi na katong nagmodular sila kay dili man gani ko kasabot sa ubang naa sa modules unsa nalang kaha ang mga bata maong ako nalang ang mag answer. Dili man sila bogo pero nadaut lang jud ang paagi nila sa pagtuon kay kana akong anak kung tutoran nako sa unsa kay maka balo man siya pero karun kay maglisud na (The children's way of learning was disturbed due to the pandemic especially the modular instruction. I cannot understand some of the content in the module, how much more the children that's why I am the one answering it. My son is not stupid or dull not to understand the lesson, it is just that they way of learning was ruined during the pandemic because my son was good and can understand right away when I tutored him before but today, he is having difficulty understanding the lesson.)

Parents shared that in their observation, children love to play. With this notion, their children cannot finish the homework or the added activities they are bringing at home. When children arrive home, they will automatically, leave their bags and play outside. This common scenario is indeed a problem not just with the parents but also with the teachers. The teacher gave assignments to master certain skills.

Theme 3: Persistence

Having the challenges experienced by the teachers and parents in the implementation of face-to-face instruction requires courage, dedication, and persistence to continue the calling of molding the learners (Patriarca, 2023). Teachers who have been in the field of education for quite some time already tested different traditional strategies that can be used in managing face-to-face instruction (Villar et al., 2022). Parents should also continue their support and involvement in the different projects and activities in school.

Teacher 4 mentioned that,

Varied strategies should be employed in managing the classroom.

Teacher 5 supported that,

One of the best ways to alleviate the challenges that teachers are experiencing is to increase the level of patience. Patience. Patience. And Patience

Teacher 1 also explained that,

Teachers should conduct daily remediation to help those learners who are struggling with numeracy and literacy.

These quotes from the teachers' experiences pave the way to understanding that in facing the emerging challenges of teachers in the implementation of face-to-face instruction, utilization of appropriate strategies, patience, and consistent remediation are the keys to assisting learners in increasing their academic performance.

Parents also provided their observations regarding their children's performance at home. Parent 2 said,

Isip usa ka ginikanan, importante kaayo nga apil kami sa pag pa edukar sa among mga anak kay ebutang ta sa ilang kinaiya, mas nakaila mi kay kami ang ginikanan ug gusto nako nga akoy modisiplina sa akong anak kung magbinadlong (As a parent, it is very important that we participate in educating our children because we know their behavior, and we know better because we are their parents and I

want to personally discipline my children.)

Parent 1 explained that,

Naay mga panahon nga dili ko kaadto sa tulungaan busa mamalihug rako sa akong silingan kay dili ko gusto nga dili maakahibalo kung unsa nay mga kasikas sa skwelahan kabahin sa performance sa akong anak (There are times when I can't go to school due to some important reasons, so I ask my neighbor in my behalf because I don't want to miss anything and on what is going on in the school especially regarding my child's academic performance.)

Parent 5 shared that,

Importante kau nga moamot jud mi kung nay amotay kay kabalo man pod mi nga naajuy makita sa mga proyekto sa mga masetra para rapod man na sa among mga anak (It is important to share whatever is being agreed regarding an amount to make the project possible and I can see the output and where my money goes and anyway, this is for my child.)

Parents are vital in helping teachers mold their children. As the common adage says, It takes a village to raise a child. This means that the parent's involvement and other stakeholders' participation can provide a good ground for the learners to attain educational outcomes.

Conclusions

The implementation of face-to-face instruction brought a myriad of changes in the educational landscape. The pessimistic effect manifested in the student's attitude and behavior and the declining progress of their learning competencies are major challenges of how the parents and teachers shared a picture of responsibility to augment these most pressing issues. The pandemic caused damage to the students' routine, delayed the skills development of the learners, and challenged the teachers' craft in classroom management and in employing innovative strategies as indicated in the theories utilized in this research. This study transpired the realization that education was greatly affected by the pandemic and the kind of traditional classroom setup now called face-to-face instruction is not the same as before. Emerging and innovative instructional strategies are required to increase the retention, focus, and motivation of the learners. This is the biggest challenge for the teachers and the parents.

This study highly recommends that monthly or quarterly counseling or interview/intervention among the learners which will be facilitated by the adviser together with the guidance counselor. Regular assessment of the learner's academic performance will be strictly monitored. Creating regular communication among parents can be initiated through the use of technological tools but should be monitored with strict compliance with professionalism and technological etiquette. School administrators may observe classes so that the prioritization of utilizing the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) allocation will be provided to those who are in need such as instructional resources that a particular grade level would need. Lastly, teachers may follow diligently the identified most essential learning competencies in teaching the learners.

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